

- The war of corals



A purple encrusting montipora coral overgrowing a brown massive porites. The two species fight using specialized attack tentacles when coming into contact, which creates the unoccupied no-man's-land trench that we can see between the two corals. The gap is about 1cm here, and depends on the length of tentacles that each species can develop.

We always think of coral reefs as peaceful places. Everything seems so calm, so warm, so clear, so beautiful. Yet, if you take the time to look closer, there are many aspects of the reef to remind you there's no truce in nature. At the end of the day, all the species cohabiting there need to find a place to live, a meal to eat, a mate to breed. The apparent peace is actually a reflection of a state of balance. A glimpse of equilibrium between all species' needs stolen within a fragment of inexorably running time between two breaths taken at the surface of the immensurable ocean. In fact, there's not much extra space to wander beyond where each species can actually be, or extra time to linger a bit longer than allotted.

I mentioned the importance of predation in coral reefs in my previous post from 22 July 2020 with the lionfish. Today, it is an illustration of competition. Many species engage in competitive interactions, because space, food, and other vital resources are not infinite in nature. Competition reaches its paroxysm in coral reefs where a high abundance and diversity of species amplify competitive interactions. This is the war of corals.

Original post: <https://www.instagram.com/p/CFSx-DfBqui/>

- When two corals come into contact



Similar to plants, most corals exhibit a fixed life-form attached to the substrate. This means survival relies critically on the ability to hold space against potential invaders. However, this is an especially hard task on the reef where every little piece of substrate is colonized by a living organism. So, what happens when two neighbouring corals grow into contact? It becomes a declaration of war. Corals, as other anemone-like sea animals, can develop attack tentacles to kill enemy tissues in their vicinity. Usually a few centimeters long, depending on the species, these tentacle attacks leave white scars of uncovered coral skeletons denuded from their living tissues.

In this picture, a branching acropora coral (top) attacked an encrusting echinopora (bottom) getting a bit too close. The whiteness of the scar indicates the recentness of the attack, probably the night before I took this picture, as dead substrates don't stay unoccupied for long on coral reefs. You can read more about this in my previous post from 29/02/2020 on the recolonization of scars left by crown-of-thorns starfish (cots) when preying upon corals.

I took this picture during my scientific study on coral competitive interactions in new caledonia

Original post: <https://www.instagram.com/p/CHHJ7X1hCMJ/>

- Coral competition at the youngest age



Competition for space and other vital resources is prevalent on coral reefs where many species cohabit in the same habitats. As living space on the reef substrate is limited, corals are often found to grow next to each other, which triggers competitive interactions early on in their life stages.

In this picture, a young colony of massive porites (purple, ~2 cm) competes with a young colony of branching acropora (orange, ~3cm).

The blue thing is my vernier-caliper which I use to measure corals at the scale of the millimeter underwater.

Original post: <https://www.instagram.com/p/CIwhH7DhF8I/>

- Competition in larger corals



All corals have to compete, but larger corals are more prone to competition.

Not all corals have the ability to reach large colony sizes. After reaching a given adult size, most species stop growing to dedicate their energy to other demographic processes such as reproduction. Some corals however maintain a continuous growth, potentially reaching very large dimensions. This is the case with this massive, >4m in diameter, beige colony of *diploastrea*. The large colony size not only reflects a high longevity, but also the ability to fight over competitors and take over reef space. However, as the colony grows, its borders increase and so does the number of potential competitors it has to confront. In this picture, the purple colony of encrusting *montipora* (~80 cm in diameter) is progressively taking over the massive *diploastrea* colony. The scene takes place in New Caledonia on the outer reef slope, outside the barrier-reef, at ~10 m water depth. This is one of my long-term study sites in the region.

Original post: <https://www.instagram.com/p/C1zfVoKBJw2/>

- A battle of acroporids



A large field of branching acroporid corals in the southwestern lagoon of New Caledonia. It is rare that corals come to occupy nearly 100% of the substrate, but some corals have a high ability to colonize available reef space, grow, and multiply using sexual reproduction and asexual propagation. This is the case with acropora, the most diversified coral genus and a major worldwide protagonist in reef construction. Acropora abundance can be particularly high in optimal reef environments and, when coral abundance increases, competitive battles for space between neighboring corals become more imminent. I counted up to 15 opponents for a single coral during my surveys in New Caledonia.

Acropora is found in all three oceanic basins of the planet, although the Atlantic Ocean's vanishing populations are highly threatened by human impacts and climate change. Healthy acroporid populations are mostly found in remote or protected reef locations that undergo little human impacts, today in big part in the Pacific Ocean, which brings hope for the capacity of acroporids to replenish reefs once human stressors are removed. The Indian Ocean has an intermediate status for acroporids and coral reef health more generally.

Stay tuned for more findings from this study. Read more about corals at the link in Bio.

Original post: <https://www.instagram.com/p/CKDWsngBHnZ/>

- The assault of the *Montipora*



What is the most ferocious coral?

This is actually a complex question to answer, as most coral species will count both the winning (invader) and losing (invaded) individuals in their ranks. After thousands of measurements on coral warfare, it comes out that competitive success depends on many factors, including not only the species, but also their growth-forms, sizes, the number of enemies, and even battleground characteristics that change over time and in space. Yet, some corals stand out as active warriors and are often seen growing over other species. A prominent one is montipora, or at least its encrusting growth-form.

Evolutionarily, encrusting corals tend to be good competitors, as unlike other species with 3-dimensional shapes (such as branching corals) that can avoid battles by growing vertically, they can only expand on a 2-dimensional space and are highly prone to territorial wars with their neighbors. So encrusting corals have to be better competitors, or to develop some other evolutionary trick, to survive.

The picture shows an encrusting montipora (about 30cm) overgrowing a massive porites (about 15cm). Because corals are slow growing, the battle can take several years. While the death of the porites is the predictable outcome, in this timeframe other forms of disturbance could be game-changers and influence the fate of these corals. For example, montipora is much more sensitive to thermal stress and bleaching, and is among the favorite prey of the predatory seastar crown-of-thorns starfish. This kind of disturbance could favor porites survival and lead to the coexistence of the two species despite their unequal abilities in direct combat. Such disturbance driven coexistence is one of the fundamental laws of biodiversity.

Picture from our study on The War of Corals. Follow link in bio to read the study or other scientific work on coral reef ecology and conservation.

Original post: <https://www.instagram.com/p/CYbztGNA3Mr/>